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Comparative effect of P source (Cow dung and Poultry Manure) on the growth, Development and Yield of Chili Pepper (*Capsicum frutescens*) in Kogi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Field trial conducted at the Kogi State University Students Research and Demonstration Farm evaluated the influence of P obtained from two sources: cow dung and poultry manure, on the growth, development and yield of chili pepper (*Capsicum frutescens*) in Anyigba, Kogi state. The experiment a 2*3 Factorial Design consisted of two sources of P (cow dung and poultry manure) supplying P, at three levels: 0 kg P/ha, 45 kg P/ha and 90 kg P/ha, with treatment replicated three times. Growth parameters (plant height, leaf area, stem girth, number of branches) responded significantly to increasing P application over the control. Significant interactions were observed between poultry manure and cow dung growth characters in chili pepper. For yield, the treatment shows significant ($P \leq 0.05$) influence of source of P on fruit weight harvested per plant as well as fruit harvested/ha, with poultry manure giving the best yield / plant as well as yield / ha. Regarding rate of P application, harvested yield was observed to increase with increasing levels of P both in poultry manure as well as in cow dung. There was also interaction between poultry manure and cow dung on chili pepper yield with the highest yield obtained in a mixture of 90kg P/ha equivalent poultry manure + 90kg P/ha equivalent cow dung. Application of higher doses of P is recommended for the cultivation of chili pepper in the study area, considering the responses obtained with increasing levels of P in the study.

Keyword: Phosphorus, cow dung, poultry manure, chili peppers, growth parameter, yield parameters

1. Introduction

1.1. Pepper

Pepper belongs to the genus *Capsicum* in the family *Solanaceae* [1]. It is cultivated and consumed worldwide, particularly in the African and Asian countries. It is rich in vitamins, especially A, B and E. They are also good sources of essential minerals such as magnesium, zinc, iron, phosphorous and potassium. They have been used for thousands of years as spices in food to enhance the flavor, colour and aroma of food. Long pepper fruits are added at a substantial quantity to produce a characteristic taste of cuisine in Nigeria and other parts of the world. In addition to boosting flavour, they are also known for their preservative and medicinal value [1].

In order to obtain high production of pepper, there is a need to address the nutrient conditions of the soil to meet the crop requirements and maintain soil fertility. Apart from the role of organic manure as a store house for plant nutrients it acts as a major contributor of Cation Exchange Capacity and as a buffering agents against undesirable p^H fluctuation, and improves the physical conditions of the soil. Organic fertilizers or their combinations at different levels has shown great influence on the growth parameters, yield components and yield of pepper [2].

1.2. Organic Manure

The poultry manure is relatively a cheap source of macro nutrients (N, P, K, Ca, Mg and S) and micronutrients (Cu, Fe, Mn and B), with the ability to increase soil Carbon, N, porosity as well as enhance soil microbial

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activity [3, 4]. Organic fertilizers are environmentally friendly; it promotes population of beneficial microorganisms and generally improves the soil health [5].

Poultry manure (PM) is the most valuable of all manures produced by livestock. The nutrient contents of poultry manure are among the highest of all animal manures, and the use of poultry manure as soil amendment for agricultural crops provides appreciable quantities of all the major plant nutrients [4]. It also improves soil biological activities, soil tilts and soil chemical properties. It was also indicated that poultry manure more readily supplies phosphorous to plants than other organic manure sources [3].

Effect of mineral nutrition on seed yield and seed quality of sweet pepper plants was reported [6]. Combinations of N, P, and K at two different rates resulted in significant differences between the two phosphorus rates on fruit and seed yield of sweet pepper [6]. However, there were no differences on plant height, foliage dry weight, and number of fruits plant⁻¹. In another study [7] on the effect of nitrogen and phosphorus application rates on seed yield of sweet pepper, phosphorus rates decreased the days to flower. Phosphorus rates alone increased the number of branches per plant. Increased P rates resulted in significant yield increases [7]; higher P rates increased considerably the number of fruits plant⁻¹ as well as seed yield [7].

It was reported that application of phosphorus at the rate of 75kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ significantly increased growth attributes like plant height and dry root weight over control in vegetable pea (*Pisum sativum*) [8]. In another field experiment on linseed, phosphorus in incremental dose increased plant height, number of branch⁻¹ plant and dry matter accumulation, while 45kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ was superior over 30 and 20kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ [9]. From the results of another field experiment [10] application of mineral P fertilizer at 46.5kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ resulted in significant increase in growth characters of chickpea over control. While [11, 12] observed that the increasing levels of phosphorus up to 30kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ significantly increased the growth attributes, viz., plant height, branches⁻¹ plant, dry matter accumulation and chlorophyll content in studied crop.

1.3.Objectives of the Research

To evaluate comparative effect of P source (Cow dung and Poultry Manure) on the growth, development and yield of Chilli pepper (*Capsicum frutescens*) in Anyigba.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1.Experimental site

A field experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm (latitude 7°15' 29"N and longitude 7°11' 12"E with an altitude of 420 m above sea level) Kogi State University Anyigba in the Guinea Savannah region of North Central Nigeria. The environment is humid, having distinct rainy and dry season. Generally rains begin in the month of March and may extend into early December, with a few showers occurring in this closing month. However, the actual plantings generally begin in April for most places. Crops grown are predominately tubers and cereals, with legumes coming into the cropping systems in the second half of the cropping season [13].

The conventional tillage operation; plough, harrow and ridges was carried out on the field before seedling transplant. Sub-plot size of 2m x 3m (6m²) were used with 0.5m leeway in between the plots. Hoe weeding complemented with hand pulling were regularly carried out to ensure weeds are kept below economic threshold.

To ascertain soil nutrient status, composite soil samples were collected to two depths: 0 – 15 cm and 15 – 30 cm, air dried, crushed and sieved with 2 mm mesh then subjected to physico-chemical properties of the soil. Percentage sand, silt and clay were determined [14], while textural class of the soil was determined using the textural triangle [15]. Total nitrogen (N) was determined using the Kjeldahl digestion method [16], while available phosphorus (P) was determined using Bray and Kurtz [17] extraction procedure. Electrical

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conductivity of the soil solution was taken using the EC electron [18]. Determination of organic carbon was by Walkley-Black wet oxidation method [19]. Exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K, and Na) were extracted with 1 N NH₄OAc buffered at pH 7.0 [20]. Soil pH was by pH meter [21] and exchangeable acidity (Al³⁺ and H⁺) was also determined [20].

2.2. Treatment and experimental design

The experiment a 2*3 Factorial design consisted of two source of P: cow dung and poultry manure, supplying three levels of P (0 kg P/ha, 45 kg P/ha and 90 kg P/ha) with the treatment replicated three times. The different rates of organic fertilizers were applied two weeks before planting for the manure to mineralize.

2.3. Data collection: Data on growth parameters were collected at 2 weeks intervals after seedling transplants:

2.3.1. Growth parameters:

Plant heights were taken as mean height of four randomly sampled and tagged stands obtained from the net plot, in accordance the procedure outlined by Amhakhian [22]. While leaf area was determined as par Mohammed *et al.* [23]. Stem girth was determined with the aid of veneer caliper at 2, 4, 6 and 8WAT as means of four (4) randomly sampled plants from the net plot. Numbers of branches were determined for four (4) selected and previously tagged plants at 2 weeks interval beginning at 4WAT.

2.3.2. Yield

Total fruits harvested from four (4) previously sampled and tagged plant stands were counted and recorded as means of four (4) stands. Harvested fruits were then weighed to obtain fresh weight of fruits and recorded as means of four (4) stands extrapolated to an hectare at 32,500 plant/ha.

2.4. Statically analysis

All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significantly different means were separated using Fishers Least Significant Differences test (F-LSD) at 5% probability level [24].

3. Results

3.1. Soil analysis

Physical and chemical properties of soil in the experimental area is presented on Table 1. The soil classification is sandy clay loam with pH values varying between 4.36 - 4.61, which was in line with pH value of most agricultural soils in Nigeria [25]. Available phosphorus was between 9.89 and 11.25 mg/kg which was below the critical value of 15 mg/kg [26, 27], thus an indication that P is a limiting factor holding back yield. In addition, organic carbon content was between 0.43 - 0.88 g/kg, which was also below the critical value of 3.4 g/kg [28] while total nitrogen was between 0.02 and 0.04 as against the critical value of 0.15 g/kg [29]. Generally the experimental land is deficient in most nutrients, often below the critical levels required for crop production.

Table 1: Result of soil analysis

Property	Depth (cm)	
	0-15	15-30
% Total Nitrogen	0.044	0.022
% Organic Carbon	0.88	0.43
% Organic Matter	1.517	0.741
pH (in KCl)	4.61	4.36
Available P (mg/kg)	11.25	9.89
Na (C mol/kg)	0.68	0.52
Mg (C mol/kg)	2.63	2.21
K (C mol/kg)	2.31	2.09
Ca (C mol/kg)	4.30	4.11

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CEC (C mol/kg)	10.95	10.07
% Silt	2.28	3.28
% Clay	21.20	22.20
% Sand	76.52	74.52
Textural Class	Sandy clay loam	Sandy clay loam

3.2.Result of organic manure analysis

Table 2 below shows nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content of the organic manures used in the experiment. Poultry manure had 2.94% N, 2.52% P and 1.39% K. Cow dung contained 1.48% N, 1.89% P and 1.02% K.

Table 2: Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium content of organic manure

Organic Manure	N%	P%	K%
Poultry manure	2.94	2.52	1.39
Cow dung	1.48	1.89	1.02

3.3.Effect of source of P, rates and their interactions on components of growth in chili pepper

3.3.1. Plant height

Data on plant heights as contained in table 3 indicate significant ($P \leq 0.05$) effect of source of P on height response in chili pepper at 6 and 8 WAT, but not at 2 and 4 WAT, while plant height was significantly influenced by increasing levels of P addition (either poultry or cow dung) at 2, 4, 6 and 8 WAT.

Based on source of P, at the end of the experiment, the highest height gain was observed in poultry manure (13.28 cm) in comparison with cow dung (8.78 cm) and control (5.46 cm). This is understandably so, considering that poultry manure had a higher amount of N, P and K as revealed in the laboratory test result (Table 2). In respect of rate of P application, in poultry manure, 90 kg P/ha gave a better performance in comparison with 45 kg P/ha at 4, 6 and 8 WAT, as well as the highest height gained at the expiration of the experiment. The same trend was observed in the cow dung application equivalent to 90 kg P/ha, when compared to 45 kg P/ha or the control. There were significant interactions between poultry manure and cow dung in respect of plant heights at 2, 4, 6 and 8WAT, with the combination of 90 kg P poultry manure + 45 kg P cow dung giving the highest height gain at the termination of the experiment.

Table 3: Effect of P source (cow dung and poultry manure) on plant height

Nutrient (P kg/ha)	Plant Height (cm)				Total height gained (cm)
	2WAT	4WAT	6WAT	8WAT	
<u>P-Source</u>					
Control	15.12	15.20	15.51	20.58	5.46
Poultry manure (P)	13.17	14.68	20.06	26.45	13.28
Cow dung (C)	15.74	16.56	19.24	24.72	8.78
LSD	0.510 ^{ns}	0.753 ^{ns}	0.817*	1.347*	-
<u>Rate of P- application</u>					
<u>Poultry manure (P)</u>					
Control	15.12	15.20	15.51	20.58	5.46
45 (P ₁)	12.70	13.81	19.37	22.81	10.11
90 (P ₂)	13.64	15.55	20.74	30.08	16.44
LSD	1.020*	1.505*	1.673*	0.693*	
<u>Cow dung (C)</u>					
Control	15.12	15.20	15.51	20.58	5.46
45 (C ₁)	17.07	17.70	20.22	21.06	3.99
90 (C ₂)	14.41	15.42	18.25	28.37	13.96

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LSD	1.020*	1.505*	1.673*	0.693*	-
Interaction (P x C)					
P ₁ C ₁	14.63	17.47	22.29	26.49	11.86
P ₂ C ₁	15.15	16.52	26.65	34.63	19.48
P ₁ C ₂	11.21	13.67	19.88	26.41	15.20
P ₂ C ₂	14.25	16.33	22.78	29.66	15.41
LSD	2.081*	2.021*	2.692*	3.771*	-

*: Significant at 5% probability; NS: Not Significant at 5% probability

3.3.2. Stem girth

Stem girth significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) responded to source of P application at 2, 4, 6 and 8 WAT (Table 4), with the best performance consistently observed in the use of poultry manure compared to cow dung. Based on rates of P application, with the use of poultry manure, the best performance was obtained with the application of 90 kg P/ha which indicates significant differences compared to other treatments throughout the experimental period. The same trend was observed in cow dung application for same treatment at 6 and 8 WAT, however in this latter case, the rate did not show supremacy over other treatments at 2 and 4 WAT, but actually lagged behind during these periods. There were significant interactions between poultry manure and cow dung in respect of stem girth at 2, 4, 6 and 8WAT.

Table 4: Effect of P source (cow dung and poultry manure) on stem girth

Nutrient (P kg/ha)	Stem Girth				Total gained (cm)
	2WAT	4WAT	6WAT	8WAT	
<u>P-Source</u>					
Control	0.88	0.94	1.29	1.87	0.99
Poultry manure (P)	0.90	1.06	1.83	2.52	1.60
Cow dung (C)	0.87	0.92	1.50	2.41	1.54
LSD	0.028*	0.045*	0.178*	0.145*	-
<u>Rate of P- application</u>					
<u>Poultry manure (P)</u>					
Control	0.88	0.94	1.29	1.87	0.99
45 (P ₁)	0.82	0.91	1.67	2.20	1.32
90 (P ₂)	0.97	1.20	1.99	2.84	1.87
LSD	0.006*	0.091*	0.355*	0.291*	-
<u>Cow dung (C)</u>					
Control	0.88	0.94	1.29	1.87	0.99
45 (C ₁)	0.89	0.93	1.47	2.03	1.14
90 (C ₂)	0.84	0.91	1.52	2.78	1.94
LSD	0.006*	0.091*	0.355*	0.291*	-
<u>Interaction (P x C)</u>					
P ₁ C ₁	0.91	1.01	1.77	2.32	1.41
P ₂ C ₁	0.83	1.02	2.19	3.52	2.69
P ₁ C ₂	0.73	1.24	2.54	3.54	2.81
P ₂ C ₂	0.86	1.38	3.42	3.62	2.76
LSD	0.121*	0.262*	1.321*	1.062*	-

*: Significant at 5% probability

3.3.3. Number of branches

Table 5 shows that P application significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) influenced branching in chili pepper at 6 and 8WAT. Based on source of the nutrient, higher plant branching was mostly observed with the application of cow dung in comparison with poultry manure. Increasing levels of P application also mostly favoured branch production

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in chili pepper, both in poultry manure and cow dung. There was significant interaction between poultry manure and cow dung on branch production at 6 and 8 WAT.

Table 5: Effect of P Source (cow dung and poultry manure) on number of branches

Nutrient (P kg/ha)	Number of Branches			
	2WAT	4WAT	6WAT	8WAT
<u>P-Source</u>				
Control	0.00	2.33	4.66	6.33
Poultry manure (P)	0.00	2.91	5.50	9.33
Cow dung (C)	0.00	4.16	3.67	13.00
LSD	Ns	0.012 ^{ns}	0.061*	1.091*
<u>Rate of P- application</u>				
<u>Poultry manure (P)</u>				
Control	0.00	2.33	4.66	6.33
45 (P ₁)	0.00	2.66	4.00	8.00
90 (P ₂)	0.00	3.16	7.00	10.66
LSD	Ns	0.140 ^{ns}	0.393*	0.505*
<u>Cow dung (C)</u>				
Control	0.00	2.33	4.66	6.33
45 (C ₁)	0.00	2.66	3.33	16.66
90 (C ₂)	0.00	5.66	4.00 ^c	9.33
LSD	ns	0.140 ^{ns}	0.393*	0.505*
<u>Interaction (P x C)</u>				
P ₁ C ₁	0.00	2.60	8.60	10.66
P ₂ C ₁	0.00	2.66	7.33	12.33
P ₁ C ₂	0.00	4.68	11.66	17.00
P ₂ C ₂	0.00	5.33	10.00	12.33
LSD	ns	0.561 ^{ns}	1.571*	2.021*

*: Significant at 5% probability; NS: Not Significant at 5% probability

3.3.4. Leaf area

Regardless of source of P, leaf area (Table 6) significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) responded to increasing P application at 6 and 8 WAT, but not at 2 and 4WAT. Cow dung did better than poultry manure in affecting leaf area in chili pepper. There were also significant interactions between poultry manure and cow dung on leaf area at 6 and 8 WAT.

3.4. Fruits yield plant

The treatment shows significant ($P \leq 0.05$) influence of source of P on fruit weight harvested per plant as well as fruit harvested/ha, with poultry manure giving the best yield/plant as well as yield/ha (Table 7). Regarding rate of P application, harvested yield was observed to increase with increasing levels of P both in poultry manure as well as in cow dung. There was also interaction between poultry manure and cow dung on chili pepper yield with the highest yield obtained in a mixture of 90kg P/ha equivalent poultry manure + 90kg P/ha equivalent cow dung.

Table 6: Effect of P source (cow dung and poultry manure) on leave area

Nutrient (P kg/ha)	Leave Area (cm ²)			
	2WAT	4WAT	6WAT	8WAT
<u>P-Source</u>				

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Control	4.57	7.93	8.94	9.80
Poultry manure (P)	5.65	9.34	13.03	15.55
Cow dung (C)	9.07	9.87	13.60	16.08
LSD	Ns	Ns	0.216*	0.342*
<u>Rate of P- application</u>				
<u>Poultry manure (P)</u>				
Control	4.57	7.93	8.94	9.80
45 (P ₁)	4.51	9.19	9.51	19.41
90 (P ₂)	6.79	9.88	16.55	11.68
LSD	Ns	Ns	0.031	0.683
<u>Cow dung (C)</u>				
Control	4.57	7.93	8.94	9.80
45 (C ₁)	10.35	11.50	15.17	16.01
90 (C ₂)	7.79	8.24	12.02	16.15
LSD	Ns	Ns	0.031	0.683
<u>Interaction(P x C)</u>				
P ₁ C ₁	6.69	6.37	15.07	15.09
P ₁ C ₂	4.82	6.12	19.20	22.72
P ₂ C ₁	6.32	6.16	20.59	20.59
P ₂ C ₂	3.90	8.27	22.02	23.51
LSD	Ns	Ns	1.731*	2.732*

*: Significant at 5% probability; NS: Not Significant at 5% probability

Discussion

That the growth components of chili pepper generally responded to P applications agrees with the results obtained by [3, 30, 31] who found out that application of organic waste, poultry droppings increases growth and yield components of Capsicum significantly. However, considering that there were no uniformity in plant heights at transplanting, drawing inference based on height variations as reflected every two weeks may be misleading; as this may not reflect the true picture of the applied treatment on this parameter. However, considering the total height gained may give a better picture of the effect of P application on the subject crop. As this latter parameter will reflect the contribution of the applied treatment to crop growth.

The positive impact of manure application either as poultry manure or cow dung over the control on growth related parameters in chili pepper must have resulted from the ability of these materials to compliment soil organic matter by adding mineral such as N, P and K which are vital to crop growth and development [2, 3, 5, 34]. The almost better performance obtained with the application of poultry manure over cow dung may have to do with higher percentage of these nutrients in poultry manure as revealed in the laboratory test analysis in table 2 [34]. This observation is in agreement with previous findings [2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 30, 34].

Table 7: Effect P source (cow dung and poultry manure) on total fresh weight

Nutrient (P kg/ha)	Fruit Yield	
	/ plant (kg)	/ hectare (kg)
<u>P-Source</u>		
Control	0.09	2,925
Poultry manure (P)	0.29	9,425
Cow dung (C)	0.21	6,825
LSD	0.000*	8.13*

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Rate of P- application

Poultry manure (P)

Control	0.09	2,925
45 (P ₁)	0.23	7,475
90 (P ₂)	0.34	11,050
LSD	0.001*	2.60*

Cow dung (C)

Control	0.09	2,925
45 (C ₁)	0.20	6,500
90 (C ₂)	0.21	6,825
LSD	0.001*	2.60*

Interaction(P x C)

P ₁ C ₁	0.22	7,150
P ₁ C ₂	0.22	7,150
P ₂ C ₁	0.27	8,775
P ₂ C ₂	0.28	9,100
LSD	0.002*	65.0*

*: Significant at 5% probability

This study further lent credence to previous observations that in order to obtain high production of pepper, there is a need to address the nutrient conditions of the soil to meet the crop requirements and maintain soil fertility [2].

Application of manure improved pepper growth *viz.*, plant height, branches / plant, dry matter accumulation and chlorophyll content which eventually resulted in improved yield over the control [11]. The improvements observed over the control as it relate to the parameters studied is an indication of the nutrient deficiency of the soil used, thus necessitating nutrient argumentation. Organic fertilizers or their combinations at different levels has shown great influence on the growth parameters, yield components and yield of chili pepper. Apart from the role of organic manure as a store house for plant nutrients it acts as a major contributor of Cation Exchange Capacity and as a buffering agents against undesirable p^H fluctuation, and improves the physical conditions of the soil [2].

Conclusion

The major constraint to crop growth and yield is soil fertility, and to peasant farmers in most parts of Nigeria soil amendments are important component in field cropping. Organic manure has been reported to give significant improvement in crop growth and yield, as it is a reservoir of nutrients which are released during mineralization, thus supplying the necessary elements for plant growth.

The results obtained in this experiment showed that P from poultry source gave the best effects on yield parameters, with higher application of P (90 kg P/ha) turning out better than (45 kg P/ha) regarding yield performance.

The experiment confirmed previous reports that poultry manure is the most valuable of all manures produced by livestock. That the nutrient contents of poultry manure are among the highest of all animal manures, and the use of poultry manure as soil amendment for agricultural crops provides appreciable quantities of all the major plant nutrients.

Therefore application of poultry manure as P source at 90kg P/ha poultry manure equivalent is recommended for the cultivation of chili pepper in the study area.

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